

Evaluation of tooth shade determination using spectrophotometry and intraoral scanning

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Abstract

This study aimed to assess the agreement between spectrophotometric and intraoral scanner-based tooth shade determination using the VITA Classical and VITA 3D-Master shade systems.

Tooth shade was determined consecutively using a spectrophotometer and an intraoral scanner in 120 healthy adults. Measurements were performed on the vestibular surfaces of 709 maxillary anterior teeth. Shade outcomes were recorded according to the VITA Classical and VITA 3D-Master systems. Inter-method agreement was evaluated using percentage agreement, Cohen's kappa coefficients, and Krippendorff's α .

Full categorical agreement was observed in 54.9% of measurements for the VITA 3D-Master system and in 62.3% for the VITA Classical system. Unweighted Cohen's kappa indicated fair-to-moderate agreement. Weighted kappa for the VITA 3D-Master system demonstrated substantial agreement, indicating that most discrepancies occurred between adjacent shade categories.

Intraoral scanner-based digital shade determination showed clinically acceptable agreement with spectrophotometric assessment. Most disagreements involved adjacent shade categories, supporting its use as a complementary method within digital workflows.

Keywords

intraoral scanner, spectrophotometry, tooth shade, VITA

Introduction

Accurate tooth shade determination is a key determinant of aesthetic success in restorative and prosthetic dentistry, particularly in the maxillary anterior region, where small color discrepancies are readily perceived (Ruan et al. 2024). Conventional visual shade selection using physical shade guides is widely used but is inherently subjective and influenced by illumination, surrounding colors, operator experience, and observer fatigue. These limitations

have driven the adoption of instrumental techniques intended to increase objectivity, repeatability, and communication accuracy between the clinic and the dental laboratory (Pecho et al. 2016; Fattouh 2021).

Spectrophotometric devices provide quantitative measurement of reflected light across wavelengths and are widely used as objective instrumental methods for clinical shade assessment due to their reduced operator dependence and improved repeatability compared with visual selection. Clinical evidence supports the reliability of den-

tal color-matching devices, including SpectroShade-based systems, in standardized settings (Kim-Pusateri et al. 2009; Tabatabaian et al. 2021; Akl et al. 2022).

In parallel, the expansion of digital dentistry has introduced intraoral scanners capable of capturing texture and color information, accompanied by software modules that estimate tooth shade according to commonly used systems. Their practical advantage is clear: shade information can be integrated directly into the digital workflow, stored, and transmitted to laboratories without additional steps. However, the reported agreement and consistency of scanner-derived shade outputs relative to spectrophotometric measurements remain variable across devices, protocols, and studied populations, as highlighted by recent clinical studies and systematic evidence syntheses (Akl et al. 2023; Elgendy et al. 2024; Floriani et al. 2024).

The most frequently used shade classification systems in clinical practice include VITA Classical and VITA 3D-Master (Sulaiman and Adebayo 2019). VITA Classical organizes tabs primarily by hue group, whereas VITA 3D-Master uses a structured concept based on value (lightness), chroma, and hue to facilitate systematic shade selection and improve distribution across tooth colors.

From a methodological perspective, shade outcomes obtained from both spectrophotometric devices and intraoral scanners are commonly reported as discrete shade categories rather than continuous color coordinates. Traditional accuracy metrics are not applicable in such cases, and agreement-based statistical approaches are required to assess consistency beyond chance across different measurement systems. Therefore, evaluating inter-method agreement is a clinically relevant approach for assessing the potential interchangeability and complementary use of instrumental shade-determination techniques.

The purpose of the present study was to assess the level of agreement between spectrophotometric and intraoral scanner-based tooth shade determination when shade outcomes are expressed using the VITA Classical and VITA 3D-Master systems.

Materials and methods

A comparative clinical study was conducted under standardized conditions with consecutive spectrophotometric and digital shade measurements.

A total of 120 patients aged 18–30 years were included (69 females and 51 males). All participants were clinically healthy, nonsmokers, and presented with intact natural dentition in the maxillary anterior region.

Inclusion criteria

Age 18–30 years; good general health; intact maxillary anterior teeth (FDI 13, 12, 11, 21, 22, and 23); absence of caries in the anterior segment; absence of restorations (fillings, crowns, and veneers) on the examined teeth; absence

of periodontal disease; absence of orthodontic deformities or malalignment affecting the anterior teeth; good oral hygiene without visible plaque or calculus.

Exclusion criteria

Caries, restorations, or prosthetic constructions on the examined teeth; pronounced extrinsic pigmentation; systemic disease or medication potentially affecting tooth color.

Shade measurements were performed on the vestibular surfaces of 709 maxillary anterior teeth (central incisors, lateral incisors, and canines). Of 720 initially assessed teeth, 11 were excluded due to scanning artifacts or inconsistencies in recorded data.

Standardization of clinical conditions and patient preparation

All participants were positioned on the same dental unit with head stabilization using a headrest to ensure a consistent head position across measurements. Shade determination was performed under natural ambient lighting without the use of the dental unit light to avoid additional illumination influencing both spectral and digital analyses.

Immediately prior to measurements, tooth surfaces were mechanically cleaned using a brush and distilled water without toothpaste, polishing pastes, or abrasive agents. This step aimed to remove extrinsic debris and provide comparable baseline conditions for both methods. Active air-drying was not routinely applied, except when required to secure an adequately dry field for intraoral scanning.

Spectrophotometric measurements were performed using a SpectroShade device (MHT Optic Research AG, Niederhasli, Switzerland) (Fig. 1). The device was calibrated

Figure 1. SpectroShade spectrophotometer (MHT Optic Research AG, Niederhasli, Switzerland).

immediately before each measurement session using the manufacturer's two-point calibration protocol with original reference tiles.

Digital shade determination was performed using a 3Shape TRIOS 4 Wireless intraoral scanner (3Shape A/S, Copenhagen, Denmark) (Fig. 2). The scanner was calibrated using the manufacturer's original calibration kit, including a calibration adapter and a double-sided color target, following the recommended calibration frequency relative to the number of scans.

Figure 2. The intraoral scanner – 3Shape TRIOS 4 Wireless (3Shape A/S, Copenhagen, Denmark).

All spectrophotometric and digital measurements were performed by the same trained operator to reduce operator-dependent variability and enhance comparability.

Spectrophotometric shade determination was conducted on the vestibular surface of each maxillary anterior tooth. The device was positioned perpendicular to the tooth surface with stable placement and a constant working distance. Correct positioning was controlled using the device's visual indicator; measurements were recorded only when the optimal position was indicated. For each tooth, the dominant shade for the vestibular surface was registered without subdivision into anatomical zones. Shades were recorded according to the VITA Classical and VITA 3D-Master systems and were used as comparative spectrophotometric outcomes for inter-method agreement analysis (Fig. 3).

After completing spectrophotometric measurements, digital shade determination was performed by intraoral

scanning of the entire maxillary arch under a dry field and standardized clinical conditions. Scanning followed the manufacturer's recommended pathway, with continuous movement along the vestibular surfaces at a uniform speed and a consistent scanner-to-surface distance. Particular attention was paid to avoiding abrupt movements, interruptions, and inclusion of soft tissues in the active scanning field to minimize digital artifacts and color inaccuracies (Fig. 4). Although the complete maxillary arch was scanned, shade analysis was restricted to the vestibular surfaces of the maxillary anterior teeth.

Digital models were processed using 3Shape Dental System CAD software (3Shape A/S, Copenhagen, Denmark) with an integrated shade-determination module. Shade values were computed for the vestibular tooth surfaces using the software-generated shade for each crown surface, reported in both the VITA Classical and VITA 3D-Master systems. In accordance with the manufacturer's recommendations, shade evaluation was based on the central area of the vestibular tooth surface, which is considered to provide the most representative color information (Fig. 5).

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS Statistics (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Descriptive distributions were reported for both shade systems and methods. For descriptive analyses and graphical presentation, shade categories representing less than 2% of the total observations were grouped into a single "Other" category to ensure adequate cell frequencies and improve interpretability. Agreement between methods was evaluated using percentage agreement (tolerance = 0), Cohen's kappa coefficient (unweighted and weighted with squared weights), and Krippendorff's α . Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. Because shade outcomes were categorical, agreement-based statistics were applied to evaluate consistency beyond chance.

Figure 3. Recorded shade with the SpectroShade spectrophotometer according to different shade guides. **A.** VITA 3D-Master shade guide; **B.** VITA Classical shade guide.

Figure 4. Intraoral scanner-generated 3D model of the maxillary anterior teeth used for digital shade analysis.

Figure 5. Digital shade analysis using intraoral scanner software with shade output in VITA Classical and VITA 3D-Master systems.

Results

Descriptive distribution of shades in VITA 3D-Master

Digital shade determination (TRIOS 4) showed pronounced clustering in mid-range VITA 3D-Master values. The most frequent shade was 1M2, observed in more than half of the examined teeth, followed by 2M3 and 0M3. Other categories occurred with substantially lower frequency, and high-chroma or extreme shades were rare (Fig. 6).

Figure 6. Descriptive distribution of shades in VITA 3D-Master.

Spectrophotometric determination (SpectroShade) showed a similar trend, with 1M2 as the dominant shade, followed by 2M3 and 0M3. Compared with intraoral scanning, spectrophotometry yielded a broader distribution and a higher frequency of intermediate categories, such as 1M1 and 2M2, indicating greater differentiation of shade characteristics.

Overall, both methods predominantly recorded medium-value and moderate-chroma shades, consistent with the young age and intact natural dentition of the study population.

Descriptive distribution of shades in VITA Classical

Digital determination (TRIOS 4) in VITA Classical showed that A1 and A2 were the most common shades, jointly accounting for the majority of examined teeth. Shade A3 also accounted for a notable proportion, whereas the other categories were infrequent.

Spectrophotometric determination demonstrated a broadly similar dominance of A-group shades, with the leading frequencies for A2, A1, and A3. In contrast to the digital results, spectrophotometry recorded a higher frequency of darker shades and identified occasional C- and D-group shades, which were absent or minimally represented in the digital measurements, suggesting greater sensitivity to less prevalent and darker categories (Fig. 7).

Figure 7. Descriptive distribution of shades in VITA Classical.

Table 1. Agreement statistics between shade determination methods.

Shade system	Percentage agreement (%)	Cohen's kappa (unweighted)	Weighted Cohen's kappa	Krippendorff's α
VITA 3D-Master	54.9	0.341	0.716	0.337
VITA Classical	62.3	0.483	0.503	0.477

Agreement between spectrophotometric and digital methods in VITA 3D-Master

Agreement analysis was performed on 709 teeth (Table 1). Percentage agreement at zero tolerance was 54.9%, indicating full categorical coincidence in just over half of the measurements. Unweighted Cohen's kappa was $\kappa = 0.341$, indicating fair agreement, and it was statistically significant ($z = 17.5$; $p < 0.001$), demonstrating agreement beyond chance. Given the ordered structure of VITA 3D-Master, weighted Cohen's kappa (squared weights) was also calculated, yielding $\kappa = 0.716$ ($z = 20.4$; $p < 0.001$), indicating substantial agreement between the methods.

Krippendorff's α for VITA 3D-Master was $\alpha = 0.337$, reflecting limited agreement under strict nominal-category interpretation.

The contrast between moderate percentage agreement and high weighted kappa indicates that a substantial fraction of mismatches occurred between adjacent categories rather than distant shades.

Agreement between spectrophotometric and digital methods in VITA Classical

Agreement analysis was performed on 709 teeth. Percentage agreement at zero tolerance was 62.3%, and full categorical agreement was observed in approximately two-thirds of cases. Unweighted Cohen's kappa was $\kappa = 0.483$, indicating moderate agreement, and it was statistically significant ($z = 23.6$; $p < 0.001$).

Weighted Cohen's kappa (squared weights) was $\kappa = 0.503$, confirming moderate agreement ($z = 13.7$; $p < 0.001$).

Krippendorff's α for VITA Classical was $\alpha = 0.477$, consistent with moderate reproducibility between the methods.

Discussion

This study compared spectrophotometric and intraoral scanner-based tooth shade determination under controlled clinical conditions and evaluated agreement across two widely used shade guides. The findings indicate that both methods demonstrated comparable shade distribution patterns, while the level of agreement varied according to the shade system structure and the statistical approach applied (Elgendy et al. 2024).

The observed concentration of shades such as 1M2 (VITA 3D-Master) and A1–A2 (VITA Classical) is consistent with the characteristics of a young adult population with intact enamel, minimal age-related darkening, and limited extrinsic staining. This pattern aligns with broader clinical evidence that lighter and moderately saturated shades dominate natural anterior tooth color distribu-

tions, particularly among younger cohorts (Demirel and Tuncdemir 2019).

In descriptive terms, SpectroShade produced a wider spread and more frequent assignment of intermediate shades (for example, 1M1 and 2M2), suggesting higher sensitivity to subtle variations (Joiner 2004). This observation is compatible with the theoretical advantage of spectrophotometry, which captures spectral reflectance and typically demonstrates strong repeatability in controlled clinical protocols (Khurana et al. 2007).

Exact categorical coincidence between methods was 54.9% for VITA 3D-Master and 62.3% for VITA Classical. These values indicate that direct one-to-one shade matching is not guaranteed when switching between device modalities. Nevertheless, weighted agreement for VITA 3D-Master was substantial ($\kappa = 0.716$), implying that mismatches usually occurred between adjacent shade categories. This is clinically important because adjacent-category discrepancies often represent small perceptual differences. These may fall below clinically unacceptable thresholds depending on the restoration context, lighting, and translucency behavior (ten Bosch and Coops 1995).

The difference between unweighted and weighted Cohen's kappa in VITA 3D-Master can be partially explained by its ordered structure, which is explicitly based on value, chroma, and hue. As a result, "near misses" are more appropriately recognized as small differences when weighted metrics are applied. The conceptual basis of the VITA 3D-Master system supports this interpretation, as value is considered the primary matching dimension, followed by chroma and hue (Paravina et al. 2015).

For VITA Classical, agreement indices were moderate (α approximately 0.48–0.50), and Krippendorff's α similarly suggested moderate reproducibility. The more hue-grouped nature of VITA Classical, along with uneven perceptual spacing between tabs, may contribute to different agreement behavior compared with VITA 3D-Master. These results are consistent with the broader literature, which shows that agreement between instrumental and digital methods is often moderate, with performance influenced by device-specific algorithms, calibration, and illumination conditions. Recent clinical and evidence synthesis studies similarly report variability in scanner shade matching, underscoring the importance of standardized protocols and awareness of methodological limitations (Akl et al. 2023). The comparatively lower values of Krippendorff's α , particularly for the VITA 3D-Master system, reflect the strict nominal-category interpretation of shade data and highlight the sensitivity of agreement coefficients to the assumed level of measurement rather than methodological inconsistency between devices.

A notable finding of this study is that spectrophotometry identified occasional darker categories and additional shade group occurrences (including C and D groups) that were

absent or minimally represented in scanner-based outputs. This may reflect differences in how devices interpret surface reflectance and translucency, the influence of texture mapping, and the averaging approach used by scanner software when providing a single shade label for an entire vestibular surface (Kim-Pusateri et al. 2009; Hein et al. 2025).

Clinically, the results support the use of intraoral scanner-based shade tools as a clinically acceptable complementary method, particularly within digital workflows where shade documentation and communication are streamlined. However, the findings also suggest that spectrophotometric assessment may remain advantageous when greater discriminatory capacity is required, when darker or less common shades are suspected, or when high-stakes aesthetic matching is critical (Moussaoui et al. 2019).

This study evaluated shade categories rather than continuous color coordinates (e.g., CIE Lab*), which may limit the resolution of difference interpretation. The population was restricted to young adults with intact anterior teeth, which may limit generalizability to older patients and teeth with restorations, wear, dehydration effects, or increased extrinsic staining. Additionally, the study relied on a single operator; while this reduces operator variability, it does not quantify inter-operator effects (Rashid et al. 2023). It should be emphasized that the present study did not aim to assess the accuracy of either method, as no absolute gold standard for tooth color exists in clinical dentistry. Instead, the analysis focused on inter-method agreement under categorical shade classification.

Conclusion

Full categorical agreement exceeded half of the measurements for both shade systems, and weighted agreement for VITA 3D-Master was substantial, indicating that most disagreements were between adjacent categories. Spectrophotometry exhibited a broader distribution of shades and greater sensitivity to intermediate and darker categories.

Within the limitations of this clinical study, intraoral scanner-based digital shade determination (3Shape TRIOS 4 with shade-analysis software) demonstrated clinically acceptable agreement with spectrophotometric assessment (SpectroShade) in maxillary anterior teeth when standardized protocols were applied.

Digital shade tools may be considered a clinically acceptable complementary method in routine clinical workflows, whereas spectrophotometric measurements remain preferable when maximal discriminatory power is required.

References

- Akl MA, Mansour DE, Zheng F (2023) The Role of Intraoral Scanners in the Shade Matching Process: A Systematic Review. *Journal of Prosthodontics* 32: 196–203. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jopr.13576>
- Akl MA, Sim CPC, Nunn ME, Zeng LL, Hamza TA, Wee AG (2022) Validation of two clinical color measuring instruments for use in dental

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization: I.L., R.T. Methodology: I.L., I.D., D.K. Investigation: I.L., I.D. Data curation: I.L., I.D. Formal analysis: I.L., D.K. Visualization: I.L., N.A. Writing – original draft: I.L. Writing – review and editing: I.L., I.D., N.A., R.T. Supervision: T.U., R.T. Funding acquisition: T.U.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

- research. *Journal of Dentistry* 125: 104223. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdent.2022.104223>
- ten Bosch JJ, Coops JC (1995) Tooth Color and Reflectance as Related to Light Scattering and Enamel Hardness. *Journal of Dental Research* 74: 374–380. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00220345950740011401>

- Demirel M, Tuncdemir M (2019) Influence of age, gender, and educational background on tooth color. *Nigerian Journal of Clinical Practice* 22: 162. https://doi.org/10.4103/njcp.njcp_442_18
- Elgendy MM, Shalaby YA, Morsy N (2024) Comparison Of The Intraoral Scanner And Visual Shade Match Accuracy In Shade Determination (Clinical Study). *Alexandria Dental Journal* 0: 0–0. <https://doi.org/10.21608/adjalexu.2024.301435.1522>
- Fattouh M (2021) Repeatability Of Visual, Spectrophotometer And Intraoral Scanner Methods In Shade Matching: A Comparative In-Vivo Study. *International Journal of Dentistry and Oral Science*: 2439–2445. <https://doi.org/10.19070/2377-8075-21000480>
- Floriani F, Jurado CA, Abuhammoud S, Vargas M, Fischer NG, Rojas-Rueda S, Lopes GC (2024) A Comparative Study of Shade-Matching Reproducibility Using an Intraoral Scanner and a Spectrophotometer. *Dentistry Journal* 12: 62. <https://doi.org/10.3390/dj12030062>
- Hein S, Nold J, Masannek M, Westland S, Spies BC, Wrbas KT (2025) Comparative evaluation of intraoral scanners and a spectrophotometer for percent correct shade identification in clinical dentistry. *Clinical Oral Investigations* 29: 39. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00784-024-06124-0>
- Joiner A (2004) Tooth colour: a review of the literature. *Journal of Dentistry* 32: 3–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdent.2003.10.013>
- Khurana R, Tredwin CJ, Weisbloom M, Moles DR (2007) A clinical evaluation of the individual repeatability of three commercially available colour measuring devices. *British Dental Journal* 203: 675–680. <https://doi.org/10.1038/bdj.2007.1108>
- Kim-Pusateri S, Brewer JD, Davis EL, Wee AG (2009) Reliability and accuracy of four dental shade-matching devices. *The Journal of Prosthetic Dentistry* 101: 193–199. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-3913\(09\)60028-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-3913(09)60028-7)
- Moussaoui H, El Mdaghri M, Gouma A, Bennani A (2019) Accuracy, Repeatability and Reproducibility of Digital Intraoral Scanner for Shade Selection: Current Status of the Literature. *Oral Health & Dental Science*. <https://doi.org/10.33425/2639-9490.1029>
- Paravina RD, Ghinea R, Herrera LJ, Bona AD, Igiel C, Linninger M, Sakai M, Takahashi H, Tashkandi E, Mar Perez M del (2015) Color Difference Thresholds in Dentistry. *Journal of Esthetic and Restorative Dentistry* 27. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jerd.12149>
- Pecho OE, Pérez MM, Ghinea R, Della Bona A (2016) Lightness, chroma and hue differences on visual shade matching. *Dental Materials* 32: 1362–1373. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dental.2016.08.218>
- Rashid F, Farook TH, Dudley J (2023) Digital Shade Matching in Dentistry: A Systematic Review. *Dentistry Journal* 11: 250. <https://doi.org/10.3390/dj11110250>
- Ruan C, Xiong J, Zhu Y, Wu Z, Lin G, Wang L (2024) Study on the Association between anterior tooth Colour Preference based on the FAHP and individual factors. *Clinical Oral Investigations* 28: 352. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00784-024-05757-5>
- Sulaiman AO, Adebayo GE (2019) Most Frequently Selected Shade For Advance Restoration Delivered In A Tertiary Hospital Facility In South Western Nigeria. *Annals of Ibadan Postgraduate Medicine* 17: 157–161. [Pubmed]
- Tabatabaian F, Beyabanaki E, Alirezai P, Epakchi S (2021) Visual and digital tooth shade selection methods, related effective factors and conditions, and their accuracy and precision: A literature review. *Journal of Esthetic and Restorative Dentistry* 33: 1084–1104. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jerd.12816>